

Students' Information Sources About San Isidro College: Their Implications to the School's Management

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How to cite this paper:

Taja-on, E., Acal, E.J., & Millalos, E. (2023) Students' Information Sources About San Isidro College: Their Implications to the School's Management. *School of Education Research Journal*, 4(1): 77-84.

Received: September 4, 2023
Accepted: October 31, 2023
Published: December 27, 2023

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ABSTRACT

Given the abundance of information available, the study highlights the importance of understanding how students access and interpret information and make judicious decisions about their education. It rationalizes why the students choose San Isidro College as their school preference. It also underscores the implications of these sources of information to SIC management. The study is anchored on social influence theory and utilizes a descriptive research design, gathering information from the incoming first-year college students enrolled during the academic year 2023-2024. The study discovered that most information stemmed from the student's parents, relatives, and friends. The second source of information came from online platforms, printed media, and other sources like the seminary, church, alums, and other institutions. The implications of these information sources to the management of San Isidro College would be to enhance and maintain strong relationships with parents, relatives, and friends; to invest further in improving its online presence utilizing various digital marketing strategies; to continue to post tarpaulins and produce flyers in targeted locations for more significant impact; to designate a focal person with knowledgeable staff who will solely work on the school's marketing; and to identify specific information sources and tailor marketing campaigns for broader dissemination.

Subject Area

Student Information Source

Keywords: *School Information; Student Information Sources*

INTRODUCTION

In an era marked by an increasingly information-rich environment, it is essential to understand how students access and interpret information to make sensible decisions regarding their education (Zehetner & Pezenka, 2022). The study anchors on the empirical gap regarding the need for comprehensive research on the specific sources students utilize to gather information on choosing schools to obtain their education. The gap includes understanding the frequency of various sources such as school websites, social media platforms, word-of-mouth, official school announcements, or other sources that students may rely on for information about their educational institution (Contreras et al., 2010). Moreover, understanding the specific sources students turn to when gathering information about the school and the influence of these sources on their perceptions and decision-making can fill an empirical gap in the literature and provide insights to improve communication and engagement between schools and students.

Based on informal interviews as to how incoming first-year students from San Isidro College (SIC) got their information about the College and why they chose this school, it showed that their choice of school did not happen in a vacuum. It happens in domestic, religious, social, and cultural settings. Domestic influence came from parents and relatives who are products of SIC. Religious influence builds on the concept that San Isidro College is the only Catholic higher education institution in Malaybalay City. As such, a good Christian education would indeed be achieved. Social influence happens when they use social networks with friends, the internet, and the word-of-mouth. The cultural environment also influences the school choice, especially since Bukidnon has several groups of indigenous peoples.

Because San Isidro College is situated where a state university is its rigid competitor, it is being chosen as students' preference indicates that it has proven itself worthy in the community. However, it still needs to work on inviting more enrollees to sustain its existence. More ventures in marketing have become a priority, and even if there is a state school that does not charge any tuition fees, with modern infrastructure and state-of-the-art facilities, SIC still manages to co-exist with the competitors around it. Its leading edge is that it is the only Catholic higher education in Malaybalay City, and it has survived the test of time, having stood for more than seven decades.

The present study looked into the students' sources of information regarding their choice of San Isidro College, considering that these students could have chosen the state school. It also asked where the students got their information and the sources that provide such information. Of course, with the rapid expansion of digital technology and the internet, students now have access to a vast array of information channels, making it crucial to analyze their perceptions and preferences when seeking information about a specific institution. By delving into the various sources the students could refer to, the findings contribute to a better understanding of the influence of information sources on students' decision-making processes when selecting a school. The implications for educational institutions, like SIC would be to enhance their marketing strategies further and improve which aspect of the school would have to be augmented or what programs to accentuate.

One objective of this study is to examine the dynamics of social influence on students' school choices. By doing so, the researchers hope to contribute to developing effective strategies for schools to understand better and meet the needs and preferences of students. This research could

provide insights into how schools can effectively engage influential individuals in students' lives and tailor their offerings to attract prospective students.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The study anchors on the Social Influence Theory by Kelman (1958), which explains how individuals are influenced by the thoughts, feelings, and behaviors of others within a social group or network. In this study, the researchers aim to understand how students choose a school and how various individuals influence their decisions in their social environment.

According to the Social Influence Theory, students' decisions about choosing a school may be influenced by their peers, family members, teachers, and other significant individuals. These people might provide opinions, recommendations, or information about different schools, which could impact the students' decisions. Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study. It is illustrated by two frames: the sources of information in the choice of San Isidro College and the implication these sources have on students' choice of school to study in. The sources of information could come from the domestic influence of parents and relatives. Their parents and relatives might have graduated from San Isidro College and found the school most appropriate for their children. The sources could also come from social networking in online platforms like the internet, Facebook™, Twitter™, Messenger™ and Instagram™. Other sources of information could come from printed and visual media like the tarpaulins posted in the school or strategic places, brochures, posters, advertisements, and others, like word of mouth from churches, seminaries, priests, laypeople, and maybe even from the aura exuded by an Isidran graduate.

Figure 1.

Conceptual schema on the information sources about San Isidro College

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study assessed the sources of information of college students at San Isidro College regarding their preference in enrolling in the aforementioned institution.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the question:

1. What are the sources of information where students obtain knowledge about San Isidro College?
2. What implications will the sources of information have on the management of San Isidro College?

METHODOLOGY

The study used the descriptive research design, obtaining information from the students regarding their knowledge of San Isidro College. The study participants were the first-year

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students who enrolled for the Academic Year 2023-2024. The study utilized the total population sampling as all first-year students were asked about their San Isidro College knowledge.

Data was gathered from the respondents through the survey during enrollment. Since all the students who processed their enrolment reports to the Dean of Students Affairs office, these students were interviewed and given the survey instrument as to their preference of choosing SIC and where they got their information about the school. The treatment of the data employed descriptive statistics, specifically frequency and percentage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Source of Information regarding San Isidro College

Table 1 presents the students response regarding the source of information about San Isidro College. The frequency and percentage of the students' responses became the basis for the analysis of findings.

Table 1.

Students source of information regarding San Isidro College

Source of Information	<i>f</i>	%
Parents/Relative/Friends	388	80.50
Online Platforms	69	14.31
Tarpaulins/Posters/Flyers/Brochures	13	2.70
Others:	12	2.49

As shown in Table 1, the most prevalent source of information came from parents, relatives, and friends, representing 80.50% of the total respondents. Many parents choose their children's school because they are also products of this school and they find their training relevant. They are alumni of San Isidro College, and their parents before them were also Isidrans; hence, they wanted their children to graduate from San Isidro as well. From their alma mater song, they resonate the lyrics... "San Isidro alma mater dear... we will love you till we die". This loyalty to the school of their alma mater is true to the older generations because they believed that the training at SIC helped them to become who they are today. The core values and the religious orientation had shaped them into better persons.

Another reason why parents choose the school for their children is because there is the common assumption that successful students are trained in school with academic quality (Lacireno-Pacquet, 2022). Parents could influence their children to study in the college or university they hear to pass or top the licensure or board exams. Parents could also influence their children as to the flagship the school bears, such as "teacher education," "accountancy," etc., or that SIC is the only school in Malaybalay offering particular courses like "civil engineering," "theology," and "values education." Other factors like religion could come into play, like "*I want my child to have good catholic training.*" Or "*I want him to be a priest.*" if they have people from their tribe sending their children to SIC, like the Bukidnons, Higa-onon, Talaandigs, etc., they want them to study in the same school. Parents' self-reports to their children about the school of their choice could motivate children's choice of SIC. This is often referred to as domestic influence, where parents and relatives are relevant and most acceptable sources of information. Parents have a direct influence on their children, and they are the ones who provide financial support.

Relatives could also be a good source of information as to the choice of school where students enroll. Like their parents, their relatives could be an alumnus of the school, or they start as working students of SIC and want to return the favor of advertising the goodness of the school. Some students who favor SIC stay in their relatives' houses as a good training ground for values education, good behavior, and God-fearing.

Friends are a very influential source of information among students since they will most likely enroll in the school where their friends are also enrolled. Peer motivation in the choice of school plays a significant role in the source of information. Sometimes, the choice is not the school but the 'classmates' they will mingle with. Students seek a school with their peers with similar beliefs, values, and ethnicity. It would give them a familiar feeling to be with the group they are much at home with. So, friends influence one another, research their school choice, and convince their peers. Consequently, they also convince their parents that working and studying with friends could enhance their academic performance.

The findings indicate that most individuals rely on personal and domestic networks to gather information. It suggests a strong influence of social connections and trusted relationships within the community. This might be because parents, relatives, and friends can provide information directly and in a personalized manner, ensuring high trust and credibility (Bentley & Metcalf, 2007; Berns, 2015; Coleman, 2018). The second source of information is done in online platforms. Research indicates that different types of information-gathering techniques are utilized by students nowadays. In this study, technological advancement shows that online platforms contribute to 14.31% of the total information received. This shows that a considerable portion of the population turns to digital sources for information. The sources could also come from social networking in online platforms, which include websites, social media, and other digital platforms, like the Internet, Facebook, Twitter, Messenger, and Instagram, where information is accessible.

Most college students own a cell phone where they can research what they want to know about. Some have computers, laptops, iPhones, iPads, and other gadgets, giving them easy access to information. These online information sources help them know the school they prefer to study in. They can connect easily with friends and agree to study in the same school. People use online sources for convenience, more comprehensive access to diverse information, and the ability to interact with others with similar interests or experiences (Westerman et al., 2014). Friends' opinions can be very influential, although informal information may need to provide a better foundation for educational choices.

The third source of information that the students identified is the materials and the paraphernalia that the school has. Tarpaulins, posters, flyers, and brochures account for 2.70% of the information received. These traditional marketing materials are still used, although to a lesser extent than other sources. Generally, the results of licensure and board exams with the faces of graduates who passed are printed on big tarpaulins and posted on the façade of the school. These tarpaulins are good advertising paraphernalia for the public because they show that the school is performing well. Much more weight is given when there are top notches, placers, and achievers because it reflects the quality and relevance of the programs offered. This suggests that there is still some effectiveness in physical forms of distribution, especially in localized areas where such materials are prominently displayed (Jalbuena et al., 2015; Nolasco & Cruz, 2016; Dagumboy, 2022).

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The remaining 2.49% is attributed to other sources, like the seminary, church, alums, and school recommendations. Although this percentage seems relatively small, it should not be neglected, as these "other" sources may still play a crucial role in providing information to specific demographics or communities. San Isidro College, for instance, caters to seminarians and values education programs. These students could have taken their sources of information from priests, nuns, and laypeople who did the dissemination from school to school, inviting them to join the vocation for the priesthood, or who visit churches and after the mass could disseminate about their congregations.

Implication to San Isidro College' Management on the Sources of Information

From the domestic sources of information like the parents, relatives, and friends, SIC could deduce that these are the groups of influencers that could affect the children's choice of school. Therefore, this group of stakeholders should be accorded respect, warm welcome, and importance when they visit the school campus or when the front-liners are dealing with them. The word-of-mouth that they could relay or propagate could have a ripple effect on the recipient. The alums who could also be parents of the children are good influencers, especially when they become successful in their field. The alumni of the school must be well-organized to project a good school image. They could advertise the school to encourage more students to enroll at SIC. They could help create projects and build infrastructure to beautify the school's image, making it inviting for prospective students. The physical structure and learning environment could be good visible motivators to entice students to enroll. These could be a gauge that the school could provide quality education.

The school management could also create more enticing incentives for parents with children enrolled at SIC. The school could organize forums for parents and the community that could be helpful for the growth of the children. Parents and alums could work hand-in-hand to influence their children to enroll at SIC. The parents and alums could provide a good scheme for scholarships to future incoming students at SIC. Since SIC is a BUACS School, it could ask for the help of the other affiliated schools to advertise and provide more information about SIC. Even the diocesan priests and laypeople could be requested to advertise SIC as the particular school for seminarians, values education, and other programs.

From social networking on online platforms, the school management could advertise the programs on Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. The school's IT department could create a kind of "ways and means" to provide massive advertisements about SIC. Informative and user-friendly websites, active social media accounts, and various digital marketing strategies could be created to reach a wider audience. A focal person could be assigned to take charge of marketing and providing regular updates to the school. Testimonies from graduates and students could be enhanced.

From other sources of information, tarpaulins could be posted in visible places where schools are located so that the graduating high schools can see the advertisements. These advertisements should be made attractive to graduating high school students. Flyers and brochures could also be posted on school bulletin boards.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The study examined the different sources of information that individuals rely on in gathering information regarding San Isidro College. It was discovered that *parents, relatives, and friends* are the most prominent sources, accounting for 80.50% of the total. This highlights the importance of personal networks in gathering information and suggests the influence of trusted relationships within the community.

Online platforms contribute 14.31% of the information received, indicating that a significant portion of the population turns to digital sources. This preference for online sources may be due to convenience, more comprehensive access to information, and the ability to interact with like-minded individuals.

Traditional *marketing materials* like tarpaulins and flyers account for 2.70%, suggesting that physical forms of distribution still have some effectiveness, especially in localized areas. People cannot underestimate the power of marketing materials because they can see these as often as possible in billboards, schools, and open spaces for advertisements.

The remaining 2.49% is attributed to other sources such as the seminary, churches, forums, word-of-mouth, or school recommendations, indicating that these sources may play a crucial role in providing information to specific demographics or communities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are given:

Since parents, relatives, and friends are the most dominant sources of information, the management of San Isidro College needs to focus on building and maintaining solid relationships with these individuals. This can be done through targeted communication, regular updates, and engaging with them.

With 14.31% of the population relying on online platforms for information, San Isidro College should invest further in improving its online presence. This can include having an informative and user-friendly website, active social media accounts, and various digital marketing strategies to reach a wider audience.

Although traditional marketing materials account for a smaller percentage, they still have some effectiveness, particularly in localized areas. San Isidro College could continue using physical distribution channels, such as tarpaulins and flyers, in targeted locations where they can have a more significant impact.

The study indicates that sources like the seminary or school recommendations are crucial in providing information to particular demographics or communities. San Isidro College could identify these specific sources and tailor their marketing campaigns to reach these audiences effectively.

San Isidro College could continuously monitor the effectiveness of different sources of information and adjust its marketing strategies accordingly. This can involve conducting regular surveys, tracking website analytics, and staying updated with current marketing trends to ensure they reach their target audience effectively.

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